

WHAT ON EARTH IS GOING WITH THE EARTH?!

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Annotation: This article discusses the consequences of global warming and climate change mainly concentrating on water shortage which brings major health, social and geopolitical problems all around the world. It stresses what some measures need to be taken at least to avoid these problems occurring at a larger scale.

Key words and phrases: water, ecology, erosion, scarcity, deforestation, climate change and government

Water is a source of life, a symbol of purity. The main source of energy for human life is water. Water is a vital factor for the body, as 70% of the body consists of water. A person can live only 4-5 days without water, and 50-60 days without food. How important drinking water is for the human body is stated in the book "Laws of Medicine" by Avicenna, and the scientist specifically stated that water is one of the necessary elements for human life. The Zoroastrian holy book "Avesta" also has a special place for nature protection.

Today, millions of people in more than 50 countries of the world are thirsty for clean drinking water. 30-40 percent of the harmful factors that have a negative impact on human health are related to the violation of water content. Nowadays, the problem of drinking water is an urgent issue in the world. By 2030, humanity will face a global water shortage. According to UNESCO's annual report on World Water Day, the problem of providing water to meet the hygienic needs of the population of the Earth is more urgent than ever after the current sanitary crisis caused by the pandemic. Because the population is increasing, new lands are being developed, industrial enterprises are being built, so the demand for fresh water is increasing. This is a sign that the level of use of water resources has reached a very dangerous point. Experts from the World Health Organization found that 80% of all diseases in the world are transmitted through contaminated water. It should be noted that infectious and parasitic diseases such as typhoid, typhoid, paratyphoid, infectious hepatitis, diarrhea, and various types of worms are caused by drinking water.

We can see that the temperature is increasing year by year, the lack of clean drinking water is becoming a common thing for the people of the world, and they are treating ecology lightly with indifference. The saddest thing is that according to the observation of the United Nations, the countries of Qatar, Israel, Lebanon, Iran, Jordan, Libya, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Eretria, United Arab Emirates, San Marino, Bahrain, India, Pakistan, Turkmenistan, Oman, Botswana, Uzbekistan more than 1.7 billion people of the world's population live in water-scarce countries. The government members of the above countries should quickly understand the dangerous consequences of water and land quality deterioration, salinization, wind and water erosion. For this, governments should increase green space and prevent cutting down of trees, rivers should not discharge industrial wastewater into the seas, switch to alternative energy faster, and create friendly relations with nature in the minds of the young generation.

Currently, worldwide deforestation, mass burning of forests, use of chemical weapons that are not suitable for the climate, are causing the withdrawal of groundwater, which is deepening the problem of water scarcity year by year.

According to experts, we can see that the increasing number of hot days exceeding +39 degrees is very dangerous for water-scarce countries and creates the basis for the rise of hidden cashiers. This is one of the biggest danger signs of climate change. Extremely hot weather is the basis for the evaporation of water on the ground and drought. The reasons for this are the increase in the population of the countries of the world, the increase in meat consumption, the use of irrigation farming in the old way, the reduction of green space, excessive damage to nature, the rapid increase in desertification, the warming of the climate, and the reduction of water reserves. At present, people are complaining about the receding of the rivers, the decrease of the water level in the reservoirs, the construction of canals, and the lack of water for irrigating crops. As a result of this, millions of people around the world are forced to move to other places, which indicates the emergence of wars and political unrest. In order to prevent these tragedies, rapidly developed and developing countries should conduct political dialogue, bring the issue of ecology to the agenda and develop it. Governments need to better assess climate change, its impacts, develop joint preventive measures, and improve the sharing of information and data.

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